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Research Article

YOUNGER GENERATION HEALTH AS IMPERATIVE OF YOUTH POLICY OF RUSSIA

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Abstract:

The article deals with the main provisions of normative documents regulating the foundations of youth policy and health policy. The basis of the analysis methodology - the normative analysis, sociological survey, the methods of logical induction and deduction - seems sufficient for meaningful conclusions. Through this methodological basis, an attempt is made to establish the relationship of these documents, and on the basis of this a conclusion is made about the declarativeness of a number of norms concerning the younger generation health. The article deals with the relationship between the Concept of Health Development in Russian Federation (2015-2020) and the Principles for the Development of the State Youth Policy in Russian Federation for the period up to 2025. They analyzed the general state of the health care system and the impact of existing limitations concerning its development and functioning on the implementation of youth policy, including on youth health. A general conclusion is made about the declarativeness, non-systemic nature and resource insecurity of modern Russian policy in the sphere of development, maintenance, and prevention of youth health care and the promotion of a healthy lifestyle.

Key words: *healthcare system, youth, youth policy, healthcare system reform, life priorities of youth.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Youth is a strategic resource of the state. The future of the country depends from its condition - physical, moral and intellectual one. The study of young people in all aspects is one of the most important tasks of modern sociological sciences. Young people are one of the main assets and the main strategic resource of the state. Caring for the young generation is one of the most important state tasks. This provision is reflected in the Fundamentals of RF state youth policy for the period until 2025, approved by the decree of the Government of Russia.

From the point of view of the state budget, it is economically beneficial to maintain the health of the able-bodied and potentially able-bodied population, since the costs on health maintaining are at a lower level than the government lost financial gain as the result of a person's retirement from the process of economic labor activity. In accordance with the Manual on social responsibility (international standard ISO 26000: 2010), a sustainable development is based on the maintenance of healthy ecosystems, social justice, on good organizational management, transparent and ethical behavior, and includes health, quality of life, the welfare of society in combination with social justice as the way of society broad expectation expression [7,8]. Thus, the doctrines of youth health development as a comprehensive program aimed at all spheres of life are necessary for modern Russian politics.

Methodology: Normative analysis, a sociological survey (questionnaire on a selective quota), general logic methods of induction and deduction and the comparative analysis of data were selected. The quota survey method was chosen because of its high efficiency, verification of the obtained data and the adequacy of the goal and the objectives of the study [11-13]. The surveys of students at the Kazan Federal University were held in 2016. The total population on the basis of reports about the contingent of students made 32 000 people [14]. The sample in each study was determined in accordance with the general statistic-probabilistic calculation rules and made 550 people [9,10]. The sample in the study of value orientations among the citizens of the Republic of Tatarstan in the field of social well-being amounted to 385 people with a total general population (the city of the Republic of Tatarstan with the population of more than 50 thousand people) of 2532896 people [15].

Thus, the object of the study was represented by Russian Federation legal framework in the field of health and youth policy, the able-bodied urban population of the Republic of Tatarstan, as well as the students of the Republic of Tatarstan at the age of 17-23 years.

RESULTS

Article 2 of Russian Federation Constitution establishes that it is a person, his rights and freedoms that are of the highest value, and the articles 7 and 41 guarantee the protection of public health and free medical care. Also, the Article 41 instructs state authorities to create special federal programs to protect and promote the healthcare of citizens [1].

There is a number of regulatory and legal acts in Russia regulating the development of the healthcare industry and the principles of its functioning. In addition to the Russian Federation Constitution the most significant law is the Federal Law "On the fundamentals of Russian Federation citizen health protection" [2]. Also, in 2014, the government approved the state program "Health Development", developed in accordance with the Concept of long-term social and economic development of Russian Federation for the period up to 2020, approved by the Russian Government Resolution No. 1662-r issued on November 17, 2008 [6].

In order to develop the youth policy in Russia the Government of Russian Federation approved the "Fundamentals of the State Youth Policy of Russian Federation until 2025" on November 29, 2014, which were also developed on the basis of the Concept of long-term social and economic development of Russian Federation for the period up to 2020 [4]. At that, it is emphasized that "new challenges related to the changes in the global world, new goals of the country social and economic development require systemic update, the development of tasks and mechanisms for state youth policy". Moreover, this document recognizes that the youth "as the most receptive and mobile part of the society supported progressive reforms and implemented them".

However, it should be noted that none of the listed documents presents the youth, its health in a separate target category. The development of healthy lifestyle among young people, despite the fact it is one of the priorities of youth policy, seems more like a declarative principle. Considering the mechanisms of the state youth policy implementation, the authors did not include in them either the problems of a healthy lifestyle development, or the problem of younger generation health protection.

In our opinion, the Concept of the long-term social and economic development in Russian Federation for the period until 2020 cannot be considered as a concept: it is devoid of complexity, the mechanisms for interagency cooperation are not worked out, there are no necessary interrelations between certain trends, there are big risks of its resource provision at the full absence of insurance mechanisms for such risks. In particular, there is no causal relationship within the framework of our study, this concept; the sections

"Health Development" and "Youth Policy", there are no special youth programs aimed at younger generation health preservation, the prevention of diseases and the propagation and development of a healthy way of life.

Thus, there is a paradoxical situation - the state recognizing the youth as the most active part of the population, realizing that it is the youth, which is one of the most important strategic resources of the country, does not take any special measures to protect its health. At the same time, the Constitution of Russian Federation separates the protection of health and medical care quite reasonably. That is, health care is a complex environment aimed at a full development of a person and an individual, which is not limited by the provision of medical services. Accordingly, the healthcare of young people as a comprehensive trend of the health protection system, whose goal is to create the necessary conditions to preserve and improve the health of young people and to maintain a healthy lifestyle, is the combination of "political, economic, legal, social, cultural, scientific, medical, sanitary hygienic and anti-epidemic nature aimed at the preservation and the strengthening of the physical and mental health of each person, the maintaining of his long-term active life, the provision of medical assistance to him in the event of health loss" [3]. At the same time, in the normative aspect and in the social-political practice of the Russian state

and society, the health problems of young people do not obtain any significant material reflections. Youth is one of the main strategic resources of the country, and the protection of health in general and youth in particular is one of the ways for economic potential preservation.

The sociological poll conducted by the authors of the article showed that the attitude towards health as one of the main values of everyday life is determined by respondents as follows:

Table 1: Recognition of health as the main value by age indicator, %

Age, years	Health	Other values
18-25	12,8	87,2
26-39	23,1	76,9
40-44	34,6	65,4
45-55	78,2	21,8
56-65	94,2	15,8

During the analysis of these indicators, we can talk about the sustainable priority of health value, starting only at the age of 50 years. If this age is not achieved, the value of health is unjustifiably overshadowed by other life priorities (Table 1). The analysis of the social needs among young people showed that health is at the very bottom of life values and priorities for a given cohort (Table 2)

Table 2: Life priorities of student youth (at the age of 17-22 years).

Life Priority	Years		
	2014	2015	2016
Make a career, achieve public recognition	27,6%	10,7%	14,3%
Be financially secure, without the need of anything	42,2%	23,1%	32,1%
Have a good friendly family, children	65,7%	27,6%	36,7%
Be healthy and live a long time	19,3%	17,8%	20,1%
Have an interesting and creative work	25,3%	19,4%	24,9%
It is difficult to answer	3,4%	1,4%	1,1%

In the absence of a motivated and developed value relationship, health is not perceived by an individual as a vital resource; therefore, as a rule, there is no individual and corporate planning in this area.

It should also be recognized that the health care system, relying only on its capabilities, is not able to change the population's value attitude to health. To solve this problem, it is necessary to include other social institutions of society, primarily state, education authorities, media, church, etc. Therefore, the statistical analysis of the state and the dynamics of the population value attitude to health is the most important component to make effective political decisions in the field of citizen health protection.

In recent years there has been a sharp increase in commercial advertising in Russia not only for medicines, but also for various methods of diagnosis and treatment. Almost all mass media of the country are actively involved in this advertisement. Unfortunately, such obtrusive advertising, occupies that niche in the information space that the medical prevention service should occupy and maintain.

In our opinion, the lack of due attention on the part of the state to medical propaganda and the development of a healthy lifestyle of the population was the main factor of self-treatment mass strategy prevalence, the ignoring of medical care by the part of the patients in a case of illness.

Today, there is a need to develop a fundamentally different system of values with the balance of public and individual interests, material and spiritual well-being, the orientation to a multi-faceted, harmonious development of an individual was provided that is not reducible only to professional success and prestigious standards of material consumption.

It is necessary to develop the following among the population:

- The dominant of value attitude to health.

Possible ways of this problem solution:

- The teaching a healthy lifestyle for citizens through various information programs, social advertising, specially adapted to different age and social groups of population;
- The study of the effectiveness concerning the influence of mass information current channels, the education system, social advertising in the creation of a developed value attitude to health;
- Development and inclusion in the program of secondary general education of a new subject on the value of health.

Although statistical collections indicate the decrease in the number of diseases from different etymologies, it is necessary to remember the decline of quantitative demographic indicators in this case, especially the number of young reference groups.

CONCLUSION:

Assessing the results of the healthcare industry development as a whole, a number of conclusions can be drawn. Despite some targeted measures taken from 2005 to 2015 in the health care system, serious problems remain that will impede the achievement of health modernization. The main of these problems are the following ones:

1. The general deficit of financial and logistical support for public health services. The result of underfunding can be the following one: a shortage of medical personnel, non-compliance with the modern standards of treatment, the inability to provide hospitals with modern equipment and supplies, the reduction of life expectancy, as the health indicator of the population depends directly on public health expenditure. For example, in 2009, the public expenditure on health in Russian Federation amounted to 5.6% of GDP, for comparison, in Portugal - 10.7%, in Greece - 10.6%, which is 2 times higher than in Russia. It should be noted that these countries have an annual GDP per capita close to Russia [5].

The concept assumes that for the period from 2010 to 2015 the volume of Russian market of health services will almost double - from 82 to 155 billion dollars. The annual growth rate will be 14% - according to this indicator, Russia will outstrip the countries of Western Europe significantly. However, RF Ministry of Finance provided the information on cost reduction by 17.8% in 2015. Modern medicine is expensive.

2. Deficiency and imbalances in the structure of medical personnel. They predict a sharp decline of medical personnel of Russia in the coming years, the reasons for this may be the following ones: the non-competitiveness of this profession in terms of wages, a high proportion of retired and pre-retirement doctors (about 50%), and demographic failure.

3. Unsatisfactory quality of medical care. Today we do not have to talk about the high quality of medical services. An inadequate qualification of medical personnel and, thus, a poor quality of medical care. One should also pay attention to an extremely low level of remuneration among the teaching staff of medical and pharmaceutical universities, which, naturally, does not stimulate the increase in the level of student education.

4. Insufficient volumes of medical assistance provided to the population under the State Guarantees Program.

5. Low volumes of high-tech medical care.

6. Ineffective management of the industry at all levels. The reasons for the failures of the health care system modernization can be underfunding and also the use of ineffective management methods.

7. The absence of a systemic, interagency approach to the development and implementation of preventive programs in the field of citizen health protection at all levels.

Nowadays, unfortunately, there is the deterioration in the state of health for all classes of diseases among such a category of citizens as children and adolescents. This contingent retains the dynamics of such socially-related diseases as alcoholism, drug addiction, tuberculosis and sexually transmitted diseases.

SUMMARY:

Thus, it can be said that the task of a new culture of health creation for the entire population, and especially for young people, becomes an urgent one in Russia to preserve health, which reduces not only the likelihood of disease occurrence, but also allows to strengthen gradually the human life force on the basis of traditional and non-traditional methods of disease prevention and treatment. Thus, from the scientific point of view, we should look for the ways to improve a healthcare system, aimed both at the study the healthcare system needs for information support, and at information quality improvement and the creation of new methods for its obtaining, storing and distribution, including the increase of available resource application efficiency.

With such modernization results, the issue of health protection among youth as a separate priority sector of public health in particular or the state policy as a whole is not provided. Thus, a number of youth policy provisions remain purely declarative.

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